

THE ROLE OF WELL-BEING IN THE PERCEIVED PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF DEAN'S SISTERS OF BS PSYCHOLOGY PROGRAM

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The Role of Well-being in the Perceived Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement of Dean's Listers of BS Psychology Program

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Abstract

This quantitative research study aimed to examine the role of well-being in students' perceived parental autonomy support and academic achievement. The study collected data through questionnaires to assess students' perceptions in these areas. The findings indicated that both mothers and fathers were perceived to provide relatively low levels of autonomy support with a higher perception of psychological control. Despite students' overall academic success, a substantial proportion reported low levels of well-being. The study showed a significantly positive correlation between the perceived parental autonomy support of mothers and fathers ($p < .001$). Additionally, significantly weak positive correlations were found between perceived maternal autonomy support and well-being ($p < 0.043$), highlighting the crucial role of the mother's involvement in promoting student well-being. However, no significant correlations were found between parental autonomy support and academic achievement for either mothers ($p = 0.963$) or fathers ($p = 0.948$), indicating the need for further investigation into the role of maternal support in academic success. Overall, the study highlights the significance of parental autonomy support, well-being, and academic achievement in students' lives. Providing students with resources and support services to improve their well-being is crucial in creating a positive learning environment that fosters engagement, motivation, and goal-setting. A comprehensive and multi-faceted approach is recommended to create a supportive and conducive environment for students' overall development and academic success.

Keywords: *parental autonomy support, psychological control, well-being, academic achievement, parental involvement*

Introduction

There has been growing concern in the Philippines over the high dropout rate, which is a troubling 83.7 percent. It translates to an alarming annual figure of 2.13 million college dropouts. To address this pressing issue, the Philippine government must undertake significant measures within the next 14 years to reverse the current enrollment pattern. Currently, the distribution of college students reveals that 80 percent are enrolled in private schools, while only 20 percent attend state universities and colleges (SUCs). The proposed goal is to strive for a more balanced distribution, with 20 percent of students enrolled in private colleges and 80 percent in SUCs, thereby ensuring broader access to quality education (Lina, 2022).

On the other hand, earning a place on the dean's list is a testament to exceptional academic achievement and unwavering commitment (Boyd et al., 2022). However, beyond recognition and accolades, high-achieving students face unique challenges that accompany their pursuit of academic excellence (Wright, 2020). This study aims to delve into the various obstacles encountered by dean's listers, shedding light on the often overlooked aspects of their college experience. By understanding these challenges, people can gain insights into the multifaceted nature of academic success and explore ways to provide meaningful support that nurtures their overall well-being.

One of the significant challenges dean's listers face is the heightened academic pressure they experience. Driven by their high standards, maintaining top grades becomes a constant concern, leading to heightened stress and fear of any potential decline (Gauthier, 2020). As a result, these students face an immense burden and anxiety that can harm their overall well-being. Effective time management is another significant hurdle for high-achieving students. Excelling academically demands a substantial investment of time and effort, often leaving little room for other activities such as extracurricular involvement, part-time jobs, or socializing (Heilferty et al., 2021). Balancing their academic commitments with personal pursuits can be daunting, often resulting in overwhelming and burnout (Kaur & Singh, 2019).

Moreover, pursuing academic excellence can inadvertently lead to social isolation for dean's listers (Heilferty et al., 2021). The rigorous dedication required to maintain their outstanding performance may cause them to miss out on social events and opportunities to connect with their peers. This sense of detachment from the college community can hinder forming meaningful relationships and support networks (Wright, 2020). Internally, high-achieving students often grapple with challenges such as perfectionism and self-doubt. The relentless pursuit of perfection and the fear of not living up to their or others' expectations can create feelings of inadequacy and anxiety. These self-imposed pressures can erode their confidence and hinder their ability to embrace their achievements fully (Boyd et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the relentless focus on academics can lead to a lack of work-life balance for dean's listers (Gauthier, 2020). Sacrificing sleep, exercise, and leisure activities in favor of dedicating more time to their studies can harm their physical and mental well-being. Neglecting self-care can result in exhaustion, decreased productivity, and reduced overall satisfaction (Wright, 2020). Despite their academic accomplishments, financial pressures can also concern high-achieving students. Pursuing excellence does not automatically alleviate the financial burdens associated with a college education, including tuition fees, textbooks, and other educational expenses.

These financial stressors can amplify the challenges faced by these exceptional students (Kaur & Singh, 2019).

The Philippines is a collective nation that raises concerns regarding the parent-child relationship dynamics (Tatel-Suatengco & Florida, 2020). Most adolescents and adults in the Philippines still live with their parents. It is then asserted in the study of Bartolome et al. (2017), to which it was stated that the relationships are characterized by children's respect for parental authority and obedience, family cohesion, and fulfillment of familial obligations. Hardships experienced throughout are also essential because, as per Karpman et al. (2020), underinvestment in children is acknowledged as a problem in low-income developing nations. As the nation's economic woes worsen, it has become increasingly common for both parents to work to provide for their families.

Academic achievement is not exclusively affected by parental autonomy support. It is heavily connected with other factors, namely understanding how emphasis should be placed on the promising goals wherein the student's learning skills, the parents' background, the teacher's quality, the influence of their peers, and the student's learning skills are discussed. Thus, this implies how the primary factors may generate outcomes because, at some other point, other characteristics may include issues like a student's capability driven by internal connectivity personality traits and all other variables that concern studies (Al-Alawi et al., 2023).

Parental autonomy support has emerged as a crucial factor in promoting positive child development. This parenting style involves encouraging children to make their own decisions and providing them with the necessary support and guidance to do so effectively. Research has shown that parental autonomy support positively affects children's development, including improved self-determination, greater well-being, better academic performance, healthy behaviors, and positive relationships with parents. One of the most notable benefits of parental autonomy support is the development of self-determination in children. Self-determination is the ability to make independent choices and take responsibility for one's actions, which is essential for success and well-being in various life domains (Van Petegem et al., 2022). Studies have shown that children who receive autonomy support from their parents are more likely to develop self-determination and feel capable of making their own choices and decisions (Van Petegem et al., 2022).

In addition to promoting self-determination, autonomy support from parents has been linked to greater well-being in children. For example, research has found that children who receive autonomy support from their parents have higher levels of happiness, life satisfaction, and self-esteem (Kashdan et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2022). They are also less likely to experience negative emotions like anxiety and depression (Katz et al., 2021). Furthermore, autonomy-supportive parenting has been associated with better academic performance in students. Studies have shown that children who receive autonomy support from their parents are more motivated and engaged in tasks and activities, which can lead to better academic outcomes (Van Petegem et al., 2022). Autonomy-supportive parents help their children develop effective study habits, set academic goals, and take ownership of their learning, which can lead to improved academic performance (Fernández-Abascal et al., 2021).

Autonomy support from parents also encourages healthy behaviors in children. For example, a study found that children who received autonomy support from their parents were likelier to engage in healthy behaviors, such as exercising regularly, eating well, and getting enough sleep (Hofmann et al., 2020). It is likely because children who feel their parents support their autonomy are likelier to take responsibility for their health and make healthy choices independently. Parental autonomy support can also promote positive relationships between parents and children. Parents supporting their children's autonomy can lead to greater trust and respect in the parent-child relationship (Katz et al., 2021). Children who feel that their parents respect their autonomy and trust their decision-making abilities are likelier to feel connected to their parents and have a positive relationship with them. Overall, parental autonomy support has numerous positive effects on children's development. Autonomy support can lead children toward success and fulfillment in various life domains by promoting self-determination, well-being, academic performance, healthy behaviors, and positive relationships with parents. Therefore, parents and caregivers should strive to provide autonomy support to their children, as it can impact their development and well-being. Therefore, this study aims to identify the level of parental autonomy support, level of well-being, the level of academic achievement of students and if these have a relationship.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the role of well-being in the perceived parental autonomy support and academic achievement of the students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of parental autonomy support perceived by the student?
2. What is the level of academic achievement of the student?
3. What is the level of well-being of the student?
4. Is there a significant relationship between perceived parental autonomy support and the academic achievement of the students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between academic achievement, well-being, and perceived parental autonomy support by the student?

Literature Review

Socio-Demographic Profile

In terms of socioeconomic status, various studies are investigated, emphasizing academic success depending on the nationalities. As

much as parental autonomy and participation are concerned, the difference is primarily impacted, such as the situation in the Philippines. Some of the considered factors were the education the parents received, human capital, and the involvement based on the parent's level of education. In line with this, it is observed how Filipino parents also utilize strategies that could help their children attain educational objectives that fit the international requirements, as mentioned by Alampay and Garcia (2019). However, what cannot be disregarded is the fact that the effects of parental support on children indicate that those who can afford to focus, such as the affluent youth, may target interventions. At the same time, different from the ones whose parental education is only lacking may tend to have minimal parental involvement. In the context of the Philippines, despite being a communicable environment, education entails an effort for the community to which higher socioeconomic status would lead to better access to resources. Overall, driven by disparities in cultural attitudes, the participation of parents is pertinent but is heavily embedded in how they are raised among households.

School

When it comes to school, the parents of the students with higher achievement are more expected to participate in school-sponsored activities than those with low achievement. In this aspect, the objective dwells upon increasingly improving the child's future. Thus, the awareness of the parents on the activities of their children may be expected. Moreover, there is also an observation that the point of view built in the school shall help the children to improve their skills further. In an institution, the parent-teacher relationship leads to more communication (Ule et al., 2015). With this in mind, the parent's roles can help promote the discovery of education wherein their trust in school is reflected by parents' in-depth involvement in the activities spearheaded by the institution.

Defining Well-being

According to Bucker et al. (2018), the concept of academic accomplishment is the consequence of schooling. In this aspect, different objectives could be linked to the well-being of the children. Academic success and students' general sense of happiness have been recognized as objectives that could show their academic performance. It is observed that a link between academic-related stress may affect the well-being of the students. The pressure that the students receive may affect their mental health. Thus, objective well-being is a huge factor because individuals with a higher tendency to be stressed may have limited subjective happiness. However, happiness is also linked to academic accomplishment, wherein one's success indicates one has competence. Therefore, the symptoms of depression and anxiety can impact the health and well-being of the students.

Defining Academic Achievement

Academic achievement pertains to the performance outcomes that affect how much a person has accomplished their goals. Having said this, the school systems may affect the cognitive objectives in different areas. Knowing that academic achievement has many indicators, it is observed that the reflection of one's intelligence may be measured by the numbers that they gain in school. At the same time, one's eligibility for higher education could be affected by academic achievement. Throughout the studies, the relevance of such achievement reflects the significance for the individual, wherein their strong relationship may indicate their determination and strength. Furthermore, academic achievement also entails comprehension, and it could only be done through the knowledge gained based on the exerted efforts to achieve such objectives within the school.

Parenting

In terms of studies, it has shown that the parents' involvement may affect the student's performance. Having said this, parents are most likely to be the ones that support their children. The parents that have invested more in the education of the students are expected to perform better, such as how direct parental involvement may help increase student achievement. Moreover, the academic outcomes may be supported based on one's parenting. In the context of the Philippines, knowing that Filipino families are commonly interdependent, prioritizing the children's education is observed. In line with this, the parents' preferred form of participation is deemed crucial because this shows the involvement that they can give to their children. This could be parental obligation and gratitude, parental supervision of schoolwork, high expectations, and social-psychological support. Overall, the different studies looked into the value of parental involvement, and positive outcomes involving factors such as motivation may be observed in the students, who may generate more success. Moreover, engagement in terms of parental involvement cannot just only increase the amount of success, it also leads to showcasing the competence that helps the children attain their goals.

Defining Parental Autonomy Support

Parental autonomy pertains to the parental behavior and attitudes that help the development of children's independence. In this aspect, the opportunities provided for the children have allowed for the support that the children receive, especially in their overall development. It is found that due to the positive impacts of parental autonomy support regarding the children's psychological well-being, the behavior exhibited by these children showcases their self-worth. This also adds up to the fact that there is greater life satisfaction knowing that the vital role of the parents encourages their children to decide on their own. This then builds a sense of competency. Thus, towards reaching goals to have better development for their children, it is found that such collectivist culture may impact the well-being and academic success of the children. Despite the autonomy support that may vary depending on the child's age, it indicates effective strategies across different developmental stages. Moreover, the approach to autonomy may be different, but the behaviors of the parents will truly impact the potential of their children.

Demographic Profile

The relevance of sex as a factor for parental autonomy support indicates that it could be a varying factor that could influence the involvement of the student's parents as the approaches are deemed vital, focusing on the attributes, especially among parents. Even in elementary schools, parental involvement is evident (Guo et al., 2018). On the other hand, the approaches could be deemed compelling, and they may be seen as a factor in parental involvement because gender differences have been relevant in terms of analyzing political, public, and scientific discourse for decades. Thus, its impact on how educational achievement may be determined depending on gender debates is observed. Meanwhile, among the selected studies, age is primordial in parental autonomy support. Evidently, Guo et al. (2018) shared about the decline in parental autonomy among students in the upper grades. Different findings demonstrated the age-specific parental involvement to showcase how cognitive domains may affect episodic memory and language processing. Mental stimulation may be affecting the strengths of the children. The results do not indicate that aging does not hinder academic achievement along with lifelong engagement to promote academic success in older adults. But, as years passed by, the parents' involvement has also become limited. Therefore, age is a factor that can be thoroughly considered especially when parents engage in activities of their children. On the other hand, a study by Nez (2015), grade level status may determine how much students devote to their assignments and how it efficiently impacts their management time. Thus, parents' perceptions may also differ. Therefore, it is implied in the study that parental autonomy that leaning on a positive aspect will most likely result in better behavior, lower rates of absenteeism, and even more favorable views. As such, the satisfaction of child's needs is provided because of the attention that they receive. Other moderators may also be involved because the relationship among grade levels may be expected to vary. The increased support may holistically motivate the individuals to achieve more, especially regarding the school's activities and initiatives.

Parents with Psychological Control

Psychological control in parenting is characterized by intrusiveness, manipulation, guilt, anxiety, and emotional manipulation to regulate children's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. In this aspect, the literature about the impact of psychological control on children indicates detrimental consequences on overall well-being. In this aspect, it has revealed how the social functioning and behavior of the children are most likely to be influenced by such elements. Thus, the children may engage in aggressive behaviors with adverse consequences, like peer relationships, reduced social competence, and peer victimization. At the same time, the nature of psychological control has demonstrated that the invalidation of children will most likely affect their development. However, cultural factors may affect these detrimental outcomes in its more profound observation. Some of these are due to the mechanisms that affect parenting practices. Therefore, observing the different tools may lead to observing and understanding parenting practices.

Defining Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is pivotal because it contributes to the development of an individual. Observing the impact of academic achievement and school-related elements is vital in this aspect. Having said this, the characteristics of the individuals may correlate to the predictors of academic performance. However, aside from that, familial factors could be linked, such as parental involvement. When parents participate, knowing that in diverse cultural contexts, resources are supported and provided by the parents since they want their children to succeed, a predictor about improvement could be taken into account. Aside from that, school-related factors may be determinants, such as the school's climate. Thus, if a school is engaging, it leads to a healthy learning environment. Other factors may be about socio-cultural context wherein one's cultural values that have been embedded on them may be the root cause behind persistence. On the other hand, some of the related aspects to be considered are peer relationships. Overall, what can be observed is that in the multitude of factors, effective strategies must be taken into account to ensure student success, especially to make academic achievement inclusive.

The State of College Students' Well-being

It is deemed valuable to take into account the well-being of college students. Due to the escalating mental health concerns, the factors contributing to their overall mental and emotional health are most likely to influence their routine. Having said this, the state of college students' well-being is a vital concern. This is because stress, financial problems, academic pressure, and social isolation may affect the children's behavior. At the same time, the students may be experiencing a crisis that could affect their growth. Nonetheless, the general problems must indicate that interventions should be made. Some factors may also involve the workshops that could lead to the mental health status of college students. Moreover, addressing these influencing factors entails thoroughly eradicating detrimental consequences for the students.

The School's Role in Helping Students Perform Better in Academics

When there is a good partnership between schools and families, students may be the significant group that will benefit. This is because their emotional and intellectual development will indicate that they are supported. This could be evident in the case of the children of school volunteers, wherein higher grades and test scores are observed in the school volunteers. Therefore, as the children are more mannered, they receive support. When they are supported, a higher chance of being successful can be observed. Moreover, good communication between parents will help the educators to be more transparent. When they become more transparent, the children may find reliable help and support. Thus, this will allow them to be more communicative, especially in facing their endeavors in life.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative descriptive correlational study will be utilized to examine the connections between the variables at hand. Specifically, this design aims to investigate the correlation and strength between two variables with no manipulation, as Curtis et al. (2021) discussed. It focuses on assessing the strength and direction of the association without manipulating variables or establishing causation.

Researchers collected numerical data using standardized instruments or surveys to measure the variables of interest. By calculating correlation coefficients, such as Pearson's correlation coefficient (r), they quantified the extent of the relationship. This type of study provides valuable insights into the patterns and connections between variables, enabling researchers to understand their interrelationships and make predictions.

Respondents

Purposeful sampling is utilized in the study. In selecting respondents, when measuring a population that is challenging to reach, informants based on a particular knowledge of, experience, and focus of the empirical study, purposeful sampling is most frequently used as discussed by Robinson (2014).

The respondents were selected based on the following criteria: (1) a BS Psychology student at NU Fairview (2) a dean's lister during both 1st term and 2nd term of Academic Year 2022-2023. All of these should be taken into consideration upon gathering data from the respondents to further investigate the relationship between parental autonomy support and academic achievement.

Bachelor of Science in Psychology Dean's listers from NU Fairview will make up the study's respondents, and their ages will range anywhere from 19 to 24 years old. It is anticipated that the total number of participants will be broken down into three distinct year levels, such as the first year, the second year, and the third year. Blocks are distributed as follows: eight in the first year—221, 222, 223, 224, 225, 226, 227, and 228—, three in the second year—211, 212, and 213—, and two in the third year—201 and 202—. On the other hand, the method of purposive sampling will decide the total number of people who responded to the survey. The respondents who are currently included on the Dean's List were given special attention during the data gathering. The students have a General Weighted Average of 3.25 to 3.49 for the second honor, and they must have a General Weighted Average of 3.49 to 4.00 for the first honor, to be placed on the Dean's List or to be considered one.

According to FindUniversity (2010), the Bachelor of Science in Psychology program is intended to teach students how to study human behavior by using the scientific approach. This allows students to gain access to the human mind and understand the complexities of it. In a larger and more observable perspective, the area provides insights into our human experiences, assists students in connecting with others, and can mean the difference between a life that is well-lived and a life that is fraught with difficulties.

Bisio (2022) went on to say that attending college can be an excellent location to develop one's personal as well as one's professional talents because it allows one to obtain in-depth knowledge in the topic of study of one's choice. In addition, having a college degree contributes to a person's social and intellectual development, which in turn makes additional options available to that individual.

Instruments

One of the most popular surveys used to gauge subjective psychological well-being is the WHO-5, a 5-item questionnaire developed by the World Health Organization, and the Perceived Parental Autonomy Support Scale (P-PASS) (Mageau et al, 2015). For the WHO-5, five simple and non-intrusive questions make up the WHO-5 questionnaire. The WHO-5's final score is between 0 and 100. 0 represents extremely low well-being, and 100 represents exceptional well-being, as discussed by Topp et al. (2015). It is a widely used, psychometrically valid indicator of one's well-being that the study will utilize in numerous research across the globe. The scale has been successfully used in various study domains and has sufficient validity as a depression screening tool and an outcome measure in therapeutic studies.

Meanwhile, P-PASS is a known instrument that was designed to measure parental autonomy support and control of late adolescents and emerging adults. With this, it is a reliable way to predict the support among the subjects consisting of 24 items, assessed on a 7-point Likert scale, from 1 (do not agree at all) to 7 (very strongly agree). Therefore, the WHO-5 and P-PASS are pertinent to the study to measure the well-being of students that mediates it from parental autonomy support and academic achievement.

A pilot study was conducted with a sample of 30 senior high school students from NU Fairview, with 10 participants each representing the strands of Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). The collected data was analyzed using SPSS software. The reliability of the data, measured through internal consistency, was found to range from 0.8 to 0.9. It indicates a high level of reliability, suggesting that the measured variables consistently captured the intended constructs. The pilot study provided valuable insights into the feasibility and effectiveness of the research design, informing potential adjustments and enhancements for future data collection and analysis.

Table 1 matrix aimed to determine the grading system employed at NU Fairview. The matrix consisted of different criteria and corresponding scoring ranges for assessing and evaluating student performance. These criteria could include test scores, assignments,

projects, participation, and overall academic performance.

Using the matrix, the researchers could classify and assign grades to the students based on their performance in each criterion. This matrix provided a structured and standardized approach to evaluating student achievement and determining their grades at NU Fairview.

Table 1. *Matrix for NU Fairview Grading System*

University Grade Point	Description	Grade Range (%)
4.00	Excellent	96-100
3.5	Very Good	90-95
3.0	Good	84-89
2.5	Above Satisfactory	78-83
2.0	Satisfactory	72-77
1.5	Fair	66-71
1.0	Pass	60-65
0.0	Repeat	< 60
R	Fail	
Dr	Officially Dropped	
Inc	Incomplete	

Table 2. *Matrix for WHO-5*

Interval	Difference	Description
1.00-1.79	0.79	Very Low
1.80-2.59	0.79	Low
2.60-3.39	0.79	Neutral
3.40-4.19	0.79	High
4.20-5.00	0.80	Very high

Table 2 matrix aimed to assess participants' well-being levels. The matrix consisted of multiple dimensions related to different aspects of well-being, including physical, emotional, social, and psychological well-being. Each dimension was evaluated using specific indicators or items that captured participants' subjective experiences and perceptions of their well-being. By collecting responses on the matrix, researchers could quantify and analyze the overall level of well-being reported by the participants. This matrix provided a comprehensive assessment of participants' well-being across various domains, allowing for a nuanced understanding of their overall quality of life and satisfaction with their well-being.

Table 3. *Matrix for Parental Autonomy Support Scale*

Interval	Difference	Description
1.00-1.85	0.85	Very Low
1.86-2.71	0.85	Low
2.71-3.57	0.85	Somewhat Low
3.58-4.43	0.85	Neutral
4.44-5.29	0.85	Somewhat High
5.30-6.15	0.85	High
6.15-7.00	0.84	Very High

The matrix from Table 3 aimed to assess the parental autonomy support perceived by students. The matrix consisted of two dimensions: "Parental Autonomy" and "Psychological Control." Each dimension was measured using Likert-scale items that captured students' perceptions of their parent's behaviors. The "Parental Autonomy" dimension focuses on supporting, encouraging, and respecting the student's decision-making and autonomy. The "Psychological Control" dimension assessed intrusive and controlling behaviors, such as manipulation, guilt-inducing strategies, or excessive monitoring. By examining the intervals on the matrix, the researchers determined the proportion of students perceiving parental autonomy support versus psychological control.

Procedure

The initial stage of the data collection phase consisted of delivering a letter of request to the program chair of the Bachelor of Science in Psychology, requesting permission to conduct the study for the consistent dean's listers for the 1st and 2nd terms of academic year 2022-2023. After receiving consent from the program chair, the researchers then delivered a letter to the school registrar to request the final general weighted average of the consistent dean's listers for the 1st and 2nd terms of academic year 2022-2023. After receiving approved letter, the researchers looked for voluntary participants, then discussed and distributed the informed consent forms to qualified candidates based on the criteria. The consent forms were returned and collected, signifying the students' participation confirmation. Administration of the WHO-5 and P-PASS was next to determine the level of well-being and perceived parental autonomy support by the student. The gathered information was compiled, tabulated, totaled, and statistically analyzed. They proceeded with conveying the findings, conclusions, and suggestions with the guidance of the adviser and validators.

Data Analysis

In research data analysis, the mean is a statistical measure representing a dataset's average value. It is obtained by summing up all the values in the dataset and dividing the sum by the total number of observations. The mean is widely used to measure the central tendency to provide an expected value that summarizes the data. It is beneficial for continuous or numerical data, allowing researchers to estimate a sample's typical or average value. The mean is a fundamental and valuable tool in research data analysis, offering insights into the observed phenomenon's central tendency and average value (Mishra et al., 2019).

Meanwhile, the standard deviation is a statistical measure used to assess the variability or spread within a dataset. The standard deviation provides valuable insights into the dispersion of data points around the mean, allowing researchers to evaluate the consistency and variability of the dataset. This measure is widely employed in hypothesis testing, constructing confidence intervals, and comparing groups or variables (Shi et al., 2020).

The correlation coefficient is a statistical measure widely used in data analysis to evaluate the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. It provides a numerical value indicating the extent to which changes in one variable coincide with changes in another. Pearson's correlation coefficient (commonly denoted as "r") is the most frequently employed measure, implying that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases proportionally. The correlation coefficient is a valuable tool in data analysis, providing insights into the strength and direction of relationships and unveiling patterns and connections within the data (Armstrong, 2019).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in research are a collection of guiding principles for designing and conducting research (Bhandari, 2022). When gathering data from people, scientists and researchers must always adhere to a set code of behavior.

Voluntary participation. Participants can opt in or out of the study at any time.

Informed consent. Before agreeing or declining to participate, participants are aware of the study's goal, advantages, risks, and funding.

Confidentiality. Researchers know the participants' identities but will keep this information confidential. They will anonymize personally identifying information so it cannot be associated with other information.

Potential for harm. All sorts of harm, including physical, social, and psychological, are maintained to an absolute minimum.

Results communication. Researchers guarantee that their work is free of plagiarism and research misconduct and that their results are appropriately represented.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1
Level of Perceived Parental Autonomy Support of the Respondents

Parental Autonomy Support (Mother)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Parental Autonomy	4.48	0.02	Somewhat low
Psychological Control	3.22	0.68	Somewhat high
N= 64			

Table 1.1 examined students' perceived levels of parental autonomy support and psychological control toward their mothers. The results reveal that, on average, the students perceive a somewhat low level of parental autonomy support (mean = 4.48, standard deviation = 0.02) and a somewhat high level of psychological control (mean = 3.22, standard deviation = 0.68). The findings suggest that, on average, the students perceive their mothers as moderately supportive of their autonomy, but there is room for improvement in fostering

a greater sense of autonomy. The mean score of 4.48 indicates a relatively low level of perceived autonomy support, which raises the importance of considering strategies to enhance parental support in this area.

On the other hand, the students perceive their mothers as exerting moderate psychological control. The mean score of 3.22 suggests that, on average, the students perceive their mothers' behaviors as undermining their autonomy to some extent. This higher score indicates the need for parents to reassess their approach to parenting and consider reducing psychological control to promote healthier parent-child dynamics (Ko et al., 2018).

Table 1.2
Level of Perceived Parental Autonomy Support of the Respondents

Parental Autonomy Support (Father)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Parental Autonomy	0.00	0.00	Very low
Psychological Control	3.00	0.90	Very high
N= 64			

Table 1.2 aimed to investigate how students perceive the parental autonomy support their fathers provided. The statistical analysis of the data revealed the following results: no significant parental autonomy support was reported, and fathers' psychological control had a mean score of 3.01 with a standard deviation of 0.89, indicating a very high level of perceived psychological control. The findings suggest that, according to the students' perceptions, there is a lack of significant parental autonomy support from their fathers. It implies that the students do not perceive their fathers as supportive in fostering their independence, decision-making, and personal agency. The absence of parental autonomy support may hinder the development of children's self-confidence, autonomy, and sense of identity (Barber et al., 2005).

Additionally, the mean score of 3.01 for fathers' psychological control indicates that the students perceive a very high level of psychological control exerted by their fathers. Psychological control encompasses behaviors that infringe upon a child's autonomy, such as manipulation, coercion, and excessive monitoring (Lansford et al., 2011). The high mean score suggests that the students perceive their fathers as exerting significant control, which can negatively affect their emotional well-being and overall development.

Table 2.0
Level of Academic Achievement of the Respondents

Academic Achievement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1 st term	3.69	0.24	Excellent
2 nd term	3.51	0.17	Very Good
N= 64			

Table 2 assessed the student's academic achievement levels based on their performance in the first and second terms. The statistical analysis of the data yielded the following results: In the first term, the students obtained a mean score of 4.018, with a standard deviation of 0.236, indicating excellent academic achievement. In the second term, the mean score was 3.84, with a standard deviation of 0.170, reflecting an excellent level of academic achievement.

Table 3.0
Level of Well-Being of the Respondents

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Overall Well-being	2.22	0.89	Low
N= 64			

Table 3 indicates that the level of well-being among the students in this study is relatively low. The mean well-being score was calculated to be 2.22, with a standard deviation of 0.89. This suggests that, on average, the students reported a lower level of well-being.

The mean score of 2.22 indicates that the students' well-being responses tended to be closer to the lower end of the scale. The standard deviation of 0.89 suggests that there was some variability in the well-being scores, but the majority of the responses clustered around the mean, indicating a consistent trend of lower well-being.

Table 4.1
Significant Relationship Between Perceived Parental Autonomy Support and The Academic Achievement of The Students

Academic Achievement	Spearman rho	p-value	Decision	Conclusion	Interpretation
Mother's P-PASS result	-0.006	0.963	Accept HO	Not significant	Very Low
Father's P-PASS result	0.008	0.948	Accept HO	Not significant	Very Low
N= 64					

Table 4.1 investigated the relationship between perceived parental autonomy support and the student's academic achievement. For the perceived maternal autonomy support (P- PASS) and academic achievement, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was computed to be -0.006 with a p-value of 0.963. Based on the hypothesis test, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was not statistically significant. These results indicate no significant relationship between perceived maternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students.

Similarly, for the perceived paternal autonomy support (P-PASS) and academic achievement, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was calculated to be 0.008 with a p- value of 0.948. The decision based on the hypothesis test was again to accept the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was not statistically significant. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students.

Table 4.2
Significant Relationship Between Perceived Parental Autonomy Support and The Academic Achievement of The Students

Mother's P-PASS result	Spearman rho	p-value	Decision	Conclusion	Interpretation
Father's P-PASS result	0.412***	<.001	Reject HO	Significant	Very High
N= 64					

Table 4.2 This study investigated the relationship between perceived parental autonomy support and the student's academic achievement. For perceived paternal autonomy support (Father's P-PASS) and its relationship to maternal autonomy support, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was calculated to be 0.412 with a p-value of less than 0.001. Based on the hypothesis test, the decision was to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was statistically significant. These results indicate a significant positive relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students.

The moderate positive correlation coefficient of 0.412 suggests that higher levels of perceived paternal autonomy support are associated with better student academic achievement. It means that when fathers provide a supportive and empowering environment encouraging autonomy and independence, students tend to perform better academically (Slemp et al., 2017). The significant p-value strengthens the confidence in the observed correlation, indicating that it is unlikely to have occurred by chance.

Table 5.1
Significant Relationship Between the Academic Achievement, Well-Being, And Perceived Parental Autonomy Support by The Student

Academic Achievement	Spearman rho	p-value	Decision	Conclusion	Interpretation
Mother's P-PASS result	-0.006	0.963	Accept HO	Not significant	Very Low
Father's P-PASS result	0.008	0.948	Accept HO	Not significant	Very Low
Well-being	0.169	0.182	Accept HO	Not significant	Very Low
N= 64					

Table 5.1 examined the relationship between academic achievement, well-being, and perceived parental autonomy support as perceived by the students. Regarding the perceived maternal autonomy support (Mother's P-PASS) and academic achievement, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was calculated to be -0.006 with a p-value of 0.963. Based on the hypothesis test, the decision was made to accept the null hypothesis (Ho) since the correlation was not statistically significant. These results indicate no significant relationship between perceived maternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students.

Similarly, for perceived paternal autonomy support (Father's P-PASS) and academic achievement, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was computed to be 0.008 with a p-value of 0.948. The decision based on the hypothesis test was again to accept the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was not statistically significant. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students.

Furthermore, for the relationship between well-being and academic achievement, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was determined to be 0.169 with a p-value of 0.182. The decision based on the hypothesis test was again to accept the null hypothesis (Ho)

because the correlation was not statistically significant. These findings indicate no significant relationship between well-being and academic achievement among the students in this study.

Table 5.2
Significant Relationship Between the Academic Achievement, Well-Being, And Perceived Parental Autonomy Support by The Student

Mother's P-PASS result	Spearman rho	p-value	Decision	Conclusion	Interpretation
Father's P-PASS result	0.412***	<.001	Reject HO	Significant	Very High
Well-being	0.253	0.043	Reject HO	Significant	High
N= 64					

Table 5.2 This study aimed to examine the relationship between academic achievement, well-being and perceived parental autonomy support as reported by the students. Regarding the perceived paternal autonomy support (Father's P-PASS) and academic achievement's relationship to maternal autonomy support, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was computed to be 0.412 with a p-value of less than 0.001. Based on the hypothesis test, the decision was made to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was statistically significant.

These results indicate a significant positive relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement among the students. Similarly, Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was determined to be 0.253 for the relationship between well-being and academic achievement, with a p-value of 0.043. Based on the hypothesis test, the decision was again to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) because the correlation was statistically significant. These findings suggest a significant positive relationship between well-being and academic achievement among the students.

Conclusions

Students perceive a somewhat low level of parental autonomy support and a somewhat high level of psychological control from their mothers. It highlights the importance of enhancing parental support for autonomy and reducing psychological control to foster healthier parent-child dynamics. The study also reveals a lack of parental autonomy support from fathers and a high level of perceived psychological control. It underscores the need for fathers to adopt autonomy-supportive behaviors and address psychological control to facilitate positive development in their children. Future research should further explore the factors influencing parental autonomy support and psychological control to inform interventions aimed at promoting supportive parent-child relationships.

Students exhibited excellent academic achievement in the first term and maintained a very good level of performance in the second term. These results demonstrate their dedication, effective learning strategies, and commitment to academic success. The consistency in scores and low standard deviations reflect the overall solid academic performance of the students. Recognizing and celebrating their accomplishments while providing appropriate support and resources are critical to further enhancing their academic potential. Future research can explore additional factors influencing academic achievement to inform targeted interventions and strategies for supporting student success. These findings highlight the students' achievements and emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive educational environment.

The interpretation of this low level of well-being suggests that the students may be facing various challenges or difficulties that impact their overall sense of well-being. These challenges could include academic stress, personal or social problems, or other factors contributing to feelings of unhappiness or dissatisfaction. The implications of low well-being on the students' functioning and academic performance should be considered. Students with lower levels of well-being may struggle with motivation, engagement, and concentration, which can have a negative impact on their academic achievement. Additionally, low well-being can also affect students' emotional and mental health, leading to further difficulties in different aspects of their lives.

The analysis investigated the relationship between perceived parental autonomy support and student academic achievement. The results indicated no significant relationship between perceived maternal autonomy support and academic achievement, as well as no significant relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement. However, it revealed a significant positive relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement. These results highlight the importance of paternal involvement and support in promoting students' academic success. Further research can explore the underlying mechanisms and develop strategies to encourage parental involvement in education to enhance student's educational outcomes.

There is no significant relationship between perceived maternal autonomy support and academic achievement, perceived paternal autonomy support and academic achievement, as well as between well-being and academic achievement among the students in this study. These results suggest that other factors not examined in this study significantly impact academic achievement and well-being. However, Table 5.2 revealed a significant positive relationship between perceived paternal autonomy support, well-being, and academic achievement. Higher levels of perceived paternal autonomy support and well-being were associated with better academic performance. These findings highlight the importance of fostering parental autonomy support and promoting well-being in enhancing students' academic success. Future research should explore additional variables and factors contributing to academic achievement and well-being and develop strategies to enhance parental involvement and support in education.

Conduct longitudinal studies to track the development of parental autonomy support, psychological control, academic achievement, and well-being over an extended period. Longitudinal research can provide insights into the long-term effects of parental support and control on students' academic and psychological outcomes. It would enable researchers to identify critical developmental stages and potential interventions to support students throughout their educational journey.

Investigate the influence of cultural and socioeconomic factors on parental autonomy support and psychological control. Different cultures and socioeconomic backgrounds may shape parenting styles differently, and understanding these variations can help design culturally sensitive interventions to enhance parental support and reduce psychological control.

Explore the role of peer relationships in students' academic achievement and well-being. Friends and peer groups can significantly influence students' attitudes toward education, motivation, and emotional well-being. Understanding how peer interactions interact with parental support and control can contribute to creating comprehensive support systems for students.

Investigate the impact of teacher support on students' academic achievement and well-being. Teachers play a crucial role in students' lives and can act as additional sources of support and encouragement. Identifying effective teacher support practices can complement parental involvement and contribute to students' overall success.

Examine how parental work-life balance affects their ability to provide autonomy support and psychological control. Balancing work and family responsibilities can be challenging for parents, and it may influence their parenting behaviors. Identifying strategies to support parents in maintaining a healthy work-life balance can positively impact their interactions with their children.

Study the influence of sibling relationships on students' development and well-being. Siblings can provide emotional support, act as role models, or contribute to conflicts within the family. Understanding the dynamics between siblings and its impact on students can help create a more supportive family environment.

Explore students' coping strategies and how they relate to their well-being and academic achievement. Understanding how students cope with stress and challenges can guide the development of targeted interventions to enhance their resilience and well-being.

Analyze the impact of educational policies on parental involvement and students' academic outcomes. Educational policies that support and encourage parental engagement can positively influence students' motivation and achievement.

Investigate the role of digital technology in facilitating parental involvement and support. With the increasing use of technology in education and communication, understanding how digital tools can be leveraged to enhance parental involvement can be valuable.

Evaluate the effectiveness of parenting programs aimed at promoting autonomy support and reducing psychological control. Design and implement evidence-based parenting programs that empower parents with skills and knowledge to create a supportive and nurturing environment for their children.

By exploring these recommendations, future research can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence students' academic achievement, well-being, and overall development, ultimately leading to more effective interventions and support systems in educational settings.

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